

DESIGN OF THE FRONT-END COMPLEX FOR A MUON COOLING DEMONSTRATOR AT CERN

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Abstract

The muon collider has great potential for enabling high-luminosity multi-TeV lepton-antilepton collisions provided low-emittance, high-intensity muon beams can be produced. Ionization cooling is the proposed technique to achieve the required muon beam emittance. The International Muon Collider Collaboration aims to demonstrate the integration and reliable operation of a 6D ionization cooling system, including RF acceleration in strong magnetic fields. This study focuses on the design of the muon production and transport systems for a Muon Cooling Demonstrator facility in the CERN TT7 tunnel. A new implementation based on the CTF3 building is also presented, offering improved layout flexibility and beam intensity. FLUKA simulations are used to optimize the target and magnetic horn geometries to maximize pion production and capture, assuming a 14 GeV proton beam from the Proton Synchrotron (PS). The transport line, designed to deliver 190 – 210 MeV/c muons into the cooling channel, consists of a short pion decay section, followed by a momentum-selecting chicane and a matching section. The chicane integrates collimation and phase-rotation systems for transverse and longitudinal tuning of the muon beam. Beam optics for the transport lattice are designed in MAD-X, with tracking studies performed using BDSIM.

MUON COOLING DEMONSTRATOR

A central challenge on the path towards a muon collider is the production of low-emittance, high-intensity muon beams — requiring efficient and compact 6D ionization cooling systems. The Muon Ionization Cooling Experiment (MICE) demonstrated transverse emittance reduction in high-emittance muon beams passing through a single, non-accelerating ionization cooling cell [1, 2]. The present study focuses on the design of the muon production and transport systems (front end) of a Muon Cooling Demonstrator, a facility designed to validate the integration and performance of 6D cooling cells composed of high-field solenoids, absorbers, dipoles, and high-gradient radiofrequency (RF) cavities [3, 4].

A conceptual layout of the Muon Cooling Demonstrator is shown in Fig. 1. The muon beam is produced through the decay of pions resulting from the interaction of protons with a target. The pions emerging from the target are captured using a magnetic horn and collected into a quadrupole-based

decay channel. At the end of this channel, a momentum-selecting chicane delivers the resulting muon beam into a beam preparation system (BPS), where the beam emittance is tuned through collimation and the beam is rotated and bunched in the longitudinal phase space using RF cavities. The prepared beam is then matched into the cooling channel. A schematic of the front-end complex is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: Conceptual schematic of the Muon Cooling Demonstrator [3].

Two siting options for the facility are under consideration at CERN — the TT7 tunnel and, more recently, the CTF3 building, which offers enhanced layout flexibility [5]. This paper reports on the front-end design progress for both sites, incorporating FLUKA-based [6] target system optimisations, MAD-X [7] optics design, and BDSIM [8] tracking simulations.

Figure 2: Conceptual schematic of the Demonstrator front-end complex.

TARGET AND PION CAPTURE

Both siting options consider exploiting the proton beam of the CERN PS for muon production. The TT7 site is envisaged to use the existing fast extraction point that delivers the PS beam to the SPS. For the CTF3 siting, a dedicated extraction system would be required and its implementation and implications are currently under study [5]. The proton beam power is limited to approximately 10 kW due to radiation safety constraints, particularly the proximity to the surface and surrounding infrastructure. The studies presented here

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assume a proton bunch intensity of 10^{13} protons, an energy of 14 GeV, an RMS bunch length of 10 ns, and a repetition rate of 4 to 5 pulses per minute. Higher bunch intensity, greater beam energy, and shorter bunch lengths are desirable for increase muon bunch intensity, but dedicated machine development studies will be required to determine the optimal beam parameters achievable in practice.

The pion production system for the two CERN options is currently conceived as a cylindrical graphite rod placed within a magnetic horn. The choice of target material and pion capture system is motivated by the relative maturity of these technologies and their extensive use in experiments that rely on proton-driven meson production.

An initial optimisation study indicated an optimum pion yield of 7.9×10^{-4} / POT using the target and parabolic horn shown in Fig. 3. The graphite rod is 90 cm long and has a 6 mm radius. The horn current was fixed at 220 kA. The pion yield was calculated for pions with momenta in the 210 – 330 MeV/c range and within a transverse acceptance of 2 mm rad in the vertical and horizontal planes. The transverse acceptance is indicated by the red ellipse on the right panel of Fig. 3. More details of the initial optimisation study can be found in [9].

Figure 3: (left) Target and horn conductor $r - z$ profiles and (right) the $x - x'$ phase space of the captured pions.

Preliminary thermal simulations indicate modest power deposition in the graphite target, which can be managed using a helium-based forced convection cooling system. These results also suggest that higher- Z materials, such as tungsten, may be viable alternatives. Building on the initial scan, a new optimisation campaign using a Bayesian optimisation framework integrated with FLUKA is now underway [10]. This study systematically explores horn geometries, target materials, and higher horn currents to identify configurations that maximise the accepted pion yield.

PION DECAY CHANNEL

Following capture by the magnetic horn, pions are transported through a decay channel designed to maximise muon production within the desired momentum range and emittance acceptance. The baseline optics for this section, common to both TT7 and CTF3 implementations, consist of three quadrupole triplets forming a 9.5 m-long lattice. The design prioritises large momentum acceptance ($\pm 50\%$) and low Twiss betatron functions to minimise beam losses during transport and decay.

An estimated 40% of the 300 MeV/c pions decay within the channel. This yields a muon beam with significant transverse emittance and energy spread. BDSIM tracking studies are used to evaluate the muon phase space at the decay channel exit. A transverse acceptance of 2 mm-rad defines the envelope for muons transported into the momentum-selecting chicane, with Fig. 4 showing the resulting beam distribution in phase space for muons in the 190-210 MeV/c momentum range. Further lattice refinements are planned to improve the usable muon yield in coordination with the chicane design.

Figure 4: (left) $x - x'$ and (right) $y - y'$ phase space of the muons in the momentum window at the end of the pion decay section. The red ellipse indicate a 2 mm-rad single particle emittance.

CHICANE

The chicane serves a dual role: it selects muons within the 190-210 MeV/c momentum window and provides a path for the extraction of unspent primary protons to a dedicated beam dump. Additionally, the final segment of the chicane is used to host the beam preparation system (BPS).

Two chicane configurations have been developed for the TT7 and CTF3 sites. The lattice components, optical Twiss functions and dispersion for the chicane segments that exclude the BPS are shown in Fig. 5. The MAD-X study used the Twiss functions of the muon beam emerging from the pion decay section as input and aimed to deliver a beam with $\beta_{x,y} = 3$ m and $\alpha_{x,y} = 0$ at the entrance to the BPS. The TT7 layout uses a three-bend geometry optimised to fit within the tight spatial constraints of the tunnel; however, the study revealed that a tunnel extension is required, and the design has been developed to minimise the extent of this modification. This layout imposes significant optical challenges, including elevated beta functions that increase losses in the apertures, incomplete dispersion suppression, and overall reduced flexibility for matching into the solenoidal beam preparation system. This could be mitigated by relaxing the spatial constraints, which would require enhanced civil engineering works to extend the tunnel.

The CTF3 version adopts a two-bend layout, enabled by the non-zero angle between the incoming proton beam and the cooling channel axis. The greater available space reduces constraints on lattice compactness, allowing the optics to maintain small beam sizes, achieve complete dispersion

suppression, and provide flexible matching — including the delivery of beams with beta functions $\beta_{x,y} < 1$ m at the entrance to the BPS.

Figure 5: Lattice components, optical Twiss functions, and dispersion for the (top) TT7 and (bottom) CTF3 chicane configurations.

Beam preparation system

Muons originating from a proton-driven horn-target system occupy a large volume in phase space and do not satisfy the transverse emittance ($\varepsilon_{\perp} \sim 2$ mm) and bunch length ($\mathcal{O}(100$ ps)) requirements imposed by the cooling channel beam dynamics. The beam preparation system performs transverse collimation and longitudinal phase-space rotation to transform the initial muon distribution into a beam suitable for injection into the cooling cells.

The system is integrated into the final segment of the chicane, and it consists of a series of solenoids that focus the beam transversely, collimators for transverse clipping, and high-gradient RF cavities to rotate the beam in the phase-energy space. A final dipole is used for momentum collimation. Fig. 6 shows a BDSIM implementation of a BPS that follows the study in [3].

The most restrictive physical aperture in the BPS is set by the iris of the RF cavities, assumed to be ~ 60 - 80 mm in radius for 704 MHz cavities. To avoid excessive collimation, the solenoidal optics must focus the beam to a minimum size in the regions with RF cavities. To obtain a beam with $\varepsilon_{\perp} \sim 2$ mm at the end of the BPS, this constraint implies a required $\beta_{\perp} < 1$ m. Preliminary optics matching studies explore solenoid configurations and field profiles that can

Figure 6: BDSIM rendering of the beam preparation system concept.

satisfy the focusing requirements and ensure integration with the upstream section of the chicane. Fig. 7 shows the field and transverse betatron function profiles for a solution that achieves $\beta_{\perp} < 1$ m in the inter-solenoid regions.

Figure 7: (green) Longitudinal magnetic field and (blue) transverse betatron function profiles within the BPS region. Using this configuration a shorter lattice containing only three solenoids is currently explored.

BDSIM tracking studies of the BPS are currently underway. Preliminary results for the CTF3 implementation indicate that $\sim 2 \times 10^6$ muons/bunch are delivered at the end of the BPS. A corresponding estimate for the TT7 configuration has not yet been completed, as the BPS optics remain under study due to the dispersive nature of the beam entering the system. However, based on tracking losses observed in the upstream part of the chicane, the delivered intensity in TT7 is expected to be up to an order of magnitude lower.

CONCLUSION

This paper reports on the ongoing design studies for the front-end beamline of the Muon Cooling Demonstrator. Conceptual layouts have been developed for two siting options at CERN — TT7 and CTF3 — with preliminary optics and tracking studies carried out to evaluate beam production, transport, collimation and phase rotation. The beam preparation system is under active development and the target system is undergoing optimisation.

The CTF3 layout benefits from greater spatial flexibility, enabling a beam intensity of $\sim 2 \times 10^6$ muons per bunch towards the cooling channel. The TT7 tunnel option is more constrained and is expected to suffer greater losses.

Future work will aim to finalise a baseline start-to-end front-end lattice. In parallel, the full lattice will be implemented in FLUKA to enable radiation studies and support the design of radioprotection and shielding systems.

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